

REPORT:

A2.1.1: Metrology Methodology

Work package 2

This report was written as part of activity 2.1.1 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit www.mfmet.eu

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1. Scope

This document shall provide a description of a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a quantity by utilizing standardized methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM (International Vocabulary of Metrology) & GUM (Evaluation of measurement data – Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement).

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A2.1.1 M6	CETIAT, NQIS, IPQ, HSG-IMIT, BHT and TUBITAK will investigate on accurate measurements of a quantity in a microfluidic device. This investigation will be based on partners' experience, a literature review and results from previous projects (EMRP JRP HLT07 MeDD and EMPIR JRP 18HTL08 MeDDII, and reports published by the MFA). Using the outcome of the investigation, CETIAT, NQIS, IPQ, HSG-IMIT, BHT and TUBITAK will define a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilizing standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM and GUM. This methodology will be used for the development of standardised measurement protocols for microfluidics in A2.2.2 and A2.3.2.	CETIAT , NQIS, IPQ, HSG-IMIT, BHT, TUBITAK

2. Normative References

ISO/IEC Guide 99:2007 - International Vocabulary of Metrology – Basic and General Concepts and Associated Terms (**VIM** 3rd edition) or JCGM 200:2012, BIPM

ISO/IEC Guide 98-3 - Evaluation of measurement data – Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement (**GUM**) or JCGM 100:2008, BIPM

The International System of Units (**SI**), 8th edition, 2006, updated in 2014, BIPM.

ISO/IEC Guide 98-4:2012 - Evaluation of measurement data – The role of measurement uncertainty in conformity assessment or JCGM 106:2012, BIPM

ISO 80000:2006 - Quantities and units

3. Metrological terms and definitions

For the purposes of this document the following terms and definitions apply.

Metrological terms and definitions are taken from the normative references VIM and GUM. In brackets are written the corresponding references and the applicable clauses. The order is alphabetically.

3.1. Calibration (VIM 2.39)

Operation, that, under specified conditions, in a first step, establishes a relation between the quantity values with measurement standards and corresponding indications with associated measurement uncertainties and, in a second step, uses this information to establish a relation for obtaining a measurement result from an indication.

3.2. Maximum permissible measurement error (MPE) (VIM 4.26)

Extreme value of measurement error, with respect to a known reference quantity value, permitted by specifications or regulations for a given measurement, measuring instrument, or measuring system.

3.3. Measured quantity value (VIM 2.10)

Quantity value representing a measurement result.

3.4. Measurement (VIM 2.1)

Process of experimentally obtaining one or more quantity values that can be reasonably be attributed to a quantity.

3.5. Measurement accuracy (VIM 2.13)

Closeness of agreement between a measured quantity value and a true quantity value of a measurand.

3.6. Measurement error (VIM 2.16)

Measured quantity value minus a reference quantity value.

3.7. Measurement method (VIM 2.5)

Generic description of a logical organization of operations used in a measurement.

3.8. Measurement precision (VIM 2.15)

Closeness of agreement between indication or measured quantity values obtained by replicate measurements on the same or similar objects under specific conditions.

3.9. Measurement procedure (VIM 2.6)

Detailed description of a measurement according to one or more measurement principles and to a given measurement method, based on a measurement model and including any calculation to obtain a measurement result.

3.10. Measurement result (VIM 2.9)

Set of quantity values being attributed to a measurand together with any other available relevant information.

3.11. Measurement repeatability (VIM 2.21)

Measurement precision under a set of repeatability conditions of measurement

3.12. Measurement uncertainty (VIM 2.26)

Non-negative parameter characterizing the dispersion of the quantity values being attributed to a measurand, based on the information used.

3.13. Metrological traceability (VIM 2.41)

Property of a measurement result whereby the result can be related to a reference through a documented unbroken chain of calibrations, each contributing to the measurement uncertainty.

3.14. Metrology (VIM 2.2)

Science of measurement and its application.

3.15. Primary measurement standard (VIM 5.4)

measurement standard established using a primary reference measurement procedure, or created as an artefact, chosen by convention.

3.16. Quantity value (VIM 1.19)

Number and reference together expressing magnitude of a quantity.

3.17. Uncertainty budget (VIM 2.33)

Statement of a measurement uncertainty, of the components of that measurement uncertainty, and their calculation and combination.

3.18. Validation (VIM 2.45)

Verification, where the specified requirements are adequate for an intended use.

3.19. Verification (VIM 2.44)

Provision of objective evidence that a given item fulfils specified requirements.

4. Technical procedure

The technical procedure shall ensure that the accurate measurement of a parameter follows the generic methodology of metrology. Among others, the technical procedure shall state the goal of the test(s) including its technical description, the measurand(s), metrological and technical requirements, the operating conditions, the acceptance criteria, and all aspects that shall have an impact on the validity of the test(s).

5. Requirements

For each test the specific operation conditions, method and procedure and the maximum permissible measurement error (MPE) of the quantity value have to be defined.

6. Specification of operation conditions

For each test the specific operation conditions have to be defined. For example, ambient temperature, atmospheric pressure, humidity.

7. Name of test method

Example: cycling pressure test or pressure burst test

7.1. Description of the test

The test has to be described in an understandable manner.

Example for the pressure burst test could be as follows (in short): increase flow until the maximum flow rate and then increase pressure stepwise with a pressure regulation valve downstream of the device until the device bursts.

7.2. Measurand

The physical quantity to be measured has to be described in detail as well as any influence factors of the measurand(s), e.g. liquid.

Examples are:

- Differential pressure between the inlet and outlet of a microfluidic device at a given flow rate of a liquid with well-known characteristics.
- Volume flow rate of demineralized water at 20°C measured upstream of the microfluidic device (object under test).

7.3. Test method

The test method has to be described in a technical manner. If possible, references to existing methods, standards, calibration guides, or any other publication (preferably available online) should be included in this section. At minimum, this section should include a description of the instrument(s) needed to perform the test. In this case, this section can include parts (or refer to) of the instrument(s) operating manual supplied by the manufacturer.

Example:

For the measurand density a densitometer is used.

7.4. Set up and test equipment

A detailed description of the setup, standards and other relevant equipment to be used for a given test or set of tests has to be given. It could be a schematic description with explicit information about each element of the setup. The type of equipment or standard, accuracy, relevant specifications and the description of how each equipment should be used.

Moreover, the position of each equipment related to the measurement of the measurand(s) has to be stated, if relevant. Example: reference pressure is measured upstream the device.

7.5. Test conditions

The necessary ambient conditions, required of the operation of the instrument(s) in their operating range, can be stated in this section, and in agreement with the test's operating conditions stated in section 6.

7.6. Preparation

This section should include the description of the preparation of the instrument(s), the fluid (or sample) and the operating conditions. For example: power on the instrument at least 30 minutes before operation, prepare a volume of 20 ml of ultra-pure water and set it at rest at 20 °C for at least 1 hour, etc.

7.7. Test procedure

This section shall describe all the steps to perform the measurement in the chronological order and with numbered bullets. If possible, pictures, schematics, screen captures should be present for each step so that the operator can quickly perform the step without reference to other documents or other pages in the document. A colour code can be used for different paragraphs in the step's description, with colours referring to different instruments, for example. Information on the number of repetitions of the test should be provided.

7.8. Calculation model

The equation for the measurand determination should be stated in this section, with a clear description of each of the equation's parameters, including all constants and variables. If possible, all constants' description should include associated expanded uncertainties (at $k=2$).

7.9. Acceptance criteria

This section should describe the acceptance criteria in order to validate the results obtained.

7.10. Uncertainty of test equipment

An uncertainty budget of each test method has to be determined according to the GUM, including the repeatability value.

It shall be calculated with a coverage factor of 2 corresponding to a coverage probability of 95 % (also stated as "k=2"). More information on other probability calculation procedures can be found in the GUM.

To perform a conformity assessment of a test result the measurement uncertainty has to fulfil the following criteria of the test uncertainty ratio in order to have a relevant statement.

The test uncertainty ratio (TUR, JCGM 106:2012) is defined as:

$TUR = \text{Maximum permissible measurement error} / \text{measurement uncertainty} (k = 2)$
JCGM 106:2012 states a ratio of 4:1, whereas in various normative documents a ratio of 5:1 is required.

7.11. Evaluation of results

Accepting or rejecting a measurement result for the conformity assessment, when the measurement error is close to the MPE can lead to an incorrect decision.

The risk of acceptance a non-confirming test can be reduced by setting an acceptance limit inside the maximum permissible measurement error. This procedure is referred to guarded acceptance in JCGM 106:2012 (8.3 Decision rules based on guard bands):

$$|\text{measurement error}| + |\text{measurement uncertainty} (k = 2)| \leq \text{MPE}$$

The following table illustrates the link between acceptance, rejection and the results with associated measurement uncertainties obtained. The arrows represent the expanded measurement uncertainties; the crosses represent the measurement errors.

Decision		← range of permissible errors →		
Acceptance		← × →		← × →
Acceptance with risk		← × →		← × →
		← × →		← × →
Rejection with risk		← × →		← × →
Rejection		← × →		← × →

8. Definition of Measurands

Definitions of measurands are taken from the normative reference ISO 80000:2006.

8.1. Mass

Mass is one of the seven base quantities of the International System of Units, SI. The symbol for mass is m , the unit is the kg.

8.2. Volume

The symbol for volume is V . The unit is the m^3 .

$$V = \iiint dx dy dz$$

Where x , y and z are cartesian coordinates.

8.3. Mass Flow rate

The symbol for mass flow rate is q_m . The unit is the kg/s.

$$q_m = \frac{dm}{dt}$$

Where m is the mass and t is time.

8.4. Volume Flow rate

The symbol for volume flow rate is q_v . The unit is the m^3/s .

$$q_v = \frac{dV}{dt}$$

Where V is the volume and t is time.

8.5. Dynamic Viscosity

The symbol for dynamic viscosity is η . The unit is the Pa.s.

$$\tau_{xz} = \frac{\eta dv_x}{dz}$$

Thus,

$$\eta = \tau_{xz} \frac{dz}{dv_x}$$

Where τ_{xz} is a shear stress in a fluid moving with a velocity gradient dv_x/dz perpendicular to the plane of shear.

8.6. Surface tension

The symbol for surface tension is σ . The unit is the N/m.

$$\sigma = \frac{dF}{dl}$$

Where F is the force component perpendicular to a line element in a surface and l is the length of the line element.

8.7. Thermodynamic Temperature

Temperature is one of the seven base quantities of the International System of Units, SI. The symbol for temperature is T , the unit is the K.

8.8. Density

The symbol for density is ρ . The unit is the kg/m^3 .

$$\rho = \frac{dm}{dV}$$

Where m is the mass and V is volume.

8.9. Pressure

The symbol for pressure is p . The unit is the Pa

$$p = \frac{dF}{dA}$$

Where dF is the force component perpendicular to the surface element of area dA

8.10. Length

The symbol for length is l . The unit is the m

8.11. Dynamic friction factor

The symbol for dynamic friction is μ .

$$\mu = F/N$$

Where F is the tangential component of the contact force (friction force) and N is the normal component of the contact force (normal force) between two sliding bodies.